

DEVELOPMENT OF PROJECTILE MOTION VLOGS

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to develop instructional material in vlogs and present new insights to multi-sensory and multimedia learning, especially in the new normal and alternative education where teachers can be physically distant from the learners. Mayer's Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning was applied to anchor the study's foundation. Furthermore, the study also aimed to improve students' knowledge of projectile motion, which was identified as the least learned competency in the past three consecutive school years. Developmental research design was utilized, which followed the modified ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation) Model in designing instructional materials. A standardized instrument, Evaluation Rating Sheet for Non-Print Materials, devised by the Department of Education- Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) to assure specific materials like vlogs, was utilized in this study. Quota sampling was employed to get 45 teachers in evaluating the projectile motion vlogs. Forty of them were Science teachers with three years and more in service and five ICT teachers. They were taken from the public junior and senior high schools within the Congressional District IB of Nueva Ecija. The projectile motion vlogs were evaluated positively and passed the content, instructional, and technical standards with very satisfactory means and above the passing rate scores which quality assured that the materials are ready to serve their purpose. However, the materials need to improve its accuracy and up-to-datedness quality and therefore need minor revisions before

implementing to the learners. Moreover, respondents commended the researcher's effort to promote Science learning engagingly.

Keywords: *Vlogs, Projectile Motion, Physics, Developmental Research, Instructional Video, Pedagogy, Innovation, Learning Material*

INTRODUCTION

The advent of technology in all levels of learning in the educational arena has dramatically transformed the teaching and learning process. This educational transformation has mostly become the key feature to continue education in the new normal during the pandemic where the spread of COVID 19 resulted to the restriction of traditional face-to-face instruction. Therefore, selecting an alternative to the teaching-learning delivery mode should be as effective and efficient as the preceding pedagogical approach.

Also, new media and globalization have significantly converted classrooms into something more appealing to today's generation or "Gen Z." As educators, it is essential to use current research to inform the many opportunities that can be offered to learners. One option in technology in education is the creation of instructional video lessons. Studies have shown that technology can enhance learning, and that video, specifically, can be a highly effective educational tool (Hsin & Cigas, 2013).

As far as this study is concerned, there are many instructional videos available throughout the internet that focused only on the lesson's serious presentation in bulk and from which very few studies are conducted to address mistakes and misconceptions in chunks and are not appropriately assessed and evaluated by experts. Therefore, to address the dilemma, education needs newer, more intense, multifaceted, and personalized perspectives, especially in teaching and learning topics considered to be least learned.

Video-blog records someone's experiences, thoughts, or opinions published online like Youtube, Facebook, and Tiktok, preferably (Cambridge Dictionary Online, n.d.). It is a spoken, asynchronous form of computer-mediated communication with a visual element (Frobenius, 2014), which has several types available throughout the internet, like instructional videos (Cristenson, 2011). Recently, vlogs were coined as "the new TV" (Buenaventura, 2015), in which the "vlogger" is a person who creates vlog content (Techterms,2011).

Vlogs can deliver learning in a most tangible way to learners and give them a self-paced approach and the time to watch and rewatch in their most convenient preference, which is previously unstudied. Vlogs have the potential to address issues of having a large class size, focus on students (Social Media and the Classroom, 2012), and attraction to the new breed of learners, and more (Kaptan & Timurlenk, 2012; Aysan,

2015). Likewise, the studies of Anil (2016) and Darmawan (2016) provided in-depth benefits in using vlogs in education. Notably, the studies concluded that vlogs: (a) had improved learner's learning performance; (b) showed learner's great interest and enthusiasm; (c) created an enjoyable, comfortable, and relaxed learning atmosphere; (d) reduced the level of learning anxiety reasonably; and (e) helped develop skills without pressure since it is a self-paced approach. However, the literature lacks strong evidence of selecting a topic, the procedure in developing the alternative, and the evaluation of vlogs by experts before the deployment of the study. Besides, choosing a topic to use in an intervention is important because it validates its effectiveness and efficiency.

Based on the consolidated fourth grading test results of Grade 9 learners for the past three years at School A, the topic of "Uniformly Accelerated Motion (UAM) in Horizontal and Vertical Dimensions of a Projectile" ranked top as least learned concept. Wherein, this is supported by the following studies claiming that the topic is challenging to deal with: (a) learners committed mistakes in solving projectile motion problems as identified by DBE (Mudau, 2014); (b) the PISA results recognizing Filipino learners with lack of scientific knowledge, skills, and processes (e.g. critical thinking, problem-solving skill, language proficiency, mathematical ability, and high vocabulary skill) (OECD, 2019; Tigere 2014; Grosser & Nel, 2013); and lastly (c) problems met by learners were not adequately addressed such as content, teachers, and environmental factors (Mudau, 2014). Therefore, the following issues should need to take a vigorous intervention to elevate the topic's learning. Moreover, this intervention should: maximize the role of a teacher who has a mastery in the subject; use as effective pedagogical approach to attract learners; excite students who are ready to learn and are skills-oriented; connect previous lessons to new where common mistakes in solving projectile are addressed (Aysan, 2015; Mudau, 2014).

Therefore, the researcher came up with the idea of bringing innovation to education. This study was conceptualized to elevate the least learned skill in Science-Projectile Motion and develop vlogs catering to instructional variation dilemmas. Meanwhile, the study only focused on the development and evaluation of vlogs in teaching projectile motion.

Research Questions

This study focused on the development and evaluation of teacher-made vlogs to improve the knowledge of students on Uniformly Accelerated Motion in Horizontal and Vertical Dimensions of a Projectile (Projectile Motion).

Specifically, the research sought to determine the following:

1. What are the notable considerations in selecting projectile motion as topic content;
2. How may the need for vlogs be analyzed;

3. How may projectile motion vlogs be designed and developed;
4. How may the experts evaluate the vlogs; and
5. What are the comments and suggestions of the experts for improvement?

METHODOLOGY

The developmental research design was employed to provide a suitable research flow and generate valid results. This aims to design, develop, and evaluate learning resources, processes, and products that must meet the criteria to be considered effective and efficient so that they can facilitate instruction (Ibrahim, 2016). Moreover, Ibrahim (2016) analyzed the four fundamental phases of developmental research related to the instructional design model in which the study was aligned. These phases were (1) Analysis, (2) Design, (3) Development, and (4) Evaluation in which Type II or Reconstructive Studies/ Model Development and Technique Development were chosen to deliver the alternative better. Hence, modified ADDIE model was employed.

The study was divided into four phases. These were: (1) Phase I: Analysis for the Need of Projectile Motion Vlogs, this first phase served as the analysis of choosing vlogs as an instructional intervention in teaching a least learned concept (Projectile Motion). This was carried out to determine the purpose of developing projectile motion vlogs and for whom it was intended. This phase was done through a thorough study of literature; (2) Phase II: Designing of Projectile Motion Vlogs, the second phase was based on Phase I (Analysis). This was the incorporation of the different principles justified in the literature review, aiming to outline what must be considered and catered to such as the DBE's recommendation in addressing the mistakes and misconceptions (2011). Vlogs' design also followed the 7 E's DOST Star Lesson Plan Exemplar to ensure that instruction flow was developmentally appropriate; (3) Phase III: Development of Projectile Motion Vlogs, at this stage, the development of the projectile motion vlogs relied on the designs already created. Planning and writing of lessons with specific learning competencies as dialogues were carried out. Filming, editing, and revising of the said instructional vlogs were carefully crafted. The making of a YouTube account and uploading of the alternative was also in this phase; and (4) Phase IV: Evaluation of Projectile Motion Vlogs by Experts, the last phase followed after the vlogs' development. Experts assessed whether the projectile motion vlogs achieve their purpose, meet the criteria to be considered effective and efficient, and decent to use through the adopted instrument- Evaluation Rating Sheet for Non-Print Materials. The improvement based on the results and suggestions of experts were also catered to in this phase.

Various research locales were identified as the place to conduct the study. These were School A and School B in Licab and other schools in the municipalities of Nueva Ecija such as School C and School D in Quezon; School E and School F in Aliaga, and School G, School H, and School I in Zaragoza. These schools fall under the locale cluster of Congressional District IB. Moreover, School A, a large school located at Poblacion

Norte in Licab, was the hotspot in the generation of test results identifying the projectile motion as the least learned concept for three (3) consecutive school years. Furthermore, the schools mentioned above also considered the topic in which students performed worst upon pre-survey conduct. In means, the identified schools were suitable and reliable to achieve the purpose of the study. The research locale was also selected purposively and conveniently since the COVID-19 pandemic is still around. To observe and follow health protocols, the municipalities surrounded within the bounds of Licab and their public high schools, as stated above, were chosen to achieve a quota of 45 respondents.

In the study, the population was divided into two major groups-Junior and Senior High School Science Teachers. They were teaching Science for at least three years. Furthermore, a 60% proportion was selected to get a sample from each group. As a result, 27 Junior High School and 13 Senior High School Science Teachers with 40 teacher-experts were identified as respondents. Same processes were also applied in selecting the five (5) ICT teacher-experts to participate in the study. Therefore, a quota of 45 experts was surveyed purposively and conveniently as respondents in the study to achieve its main objectives- to develop and evaluate projectile motion vlogs.

The primary instrument employed in the study was the use of the Survey Questionnaire. As defined by the author, the questionnaire consists of a series of questions that serve as a quick and efficient way of gathering a large amount of data from the respondents (Macleod, 2018). Meanwhile, the employed instrument was further divided into two sections: (1) the evaluation of learning resources adopted from the DepEd-LRMDS; and (2) the comments and suggestions of experts on the learning resource.

The Department of Education's Guidelines and Processes for Learning Resource Management and Development System (LRDMS) Assessment and Evaluation aims to identify quality assured learning resources. Therefore, they developed high-quality assessment and evaluation tools for different learning resources to ensure this. This convinced the researcher to use the LRMDS Assessment and Evaluation System tool since the study shared the same objective and principle. Among the assessment and evaluation systems, the Evaluation for Non- Print Materials was selected and adopted as the study's main instrument since the characteristics of educational vlogs satisfied the said evaluation tool, especially the type or kind of material developed. Furthermore, the evaluation rating sheet for non-print materials was divided into the following four quality factors: (a) Factor A: Content Quality - consists of 10-item descriptors to determine the materials' ability to display appropriate and organize mastery of the lesson and promote understanding of the topic being discussed; (b) Factor B: Instructional Quality - consists of 10-item descriptors to determine the materials' ability to display purpose as pedagogical innovation for a classroom setting. It should be learner-friendly; (c) Factor C: Technical Quality - consists of 13-item descriptors to determine the materials' ability to display good visual and audio presentations that enhance the learning of the topic and make it appealing to learners; and (d) Factor D: Accuracy and Up-to-datedness

Information Quality - consists of 4-item conditions to determine the materials' ability to display current, accurate, and error-free content presentation.

After the analysis, design, and development phases of projectile motion vlogs, and when the thesis adviser and the panel members' consultation and recommendation were established, the evaluation phase was performed to start the data gathering procedures. Upon the Graduate School's approval to deploy the link of the survey questionnaire in Google form, a letter of consent to the respondents' school heads was sent priorly.

After the respondents were selected as experts to evaluate the learning resource or educational vlogs, a link of the survey questionnaire via Google Form was sent thru their FB Messenger or Personal E-mail Address to observe less physical contact because of the pandemic. When a quota of 45 respondents was surveyed, raw results were generated rapidly and the survey was stopped.

Raw results were treated using the appropriate statistical treatment to provide the exact data needed for the study. For qualitative data, they were convened into themes for each transcript. The data were presented and organized in tabular presentations for the easy development of the study's conclusion and recommendation.

RESULTS

Notable Considerations in Selecting Projectile Motion as Topic Content

Projectile motion is a study where objects or bodies are projected through a gravitational ground and exist in horizontal and vertical components or dimensions. In the Philippine education, this topic is taught in Grade 9 under the K to 12 curriculum. However, based on the test results, this topic ranked first (1st) as the least learned concept having mean percentage score (MPS) of more than ten points below the passing rate for three consecutive school years (School A, 2016-2019).

Table 1.
Test Results for Three Consecutive School Years

Year	N	Mean	MPL	MPS	SD
2016-2017	346	19.73	39.46	40.67	11.57
2017-2018	357	19.00	38.01	39.25	10.14
2018-2019	378	19.57	39.13	40.35	9.66

Analysis of the Need for Vlogs

Table 2.
Literature Analysis of the Need for Vlogs

Theme	Percentage
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1. Benefits of Using Vlogs in Learning a Topic (Data Reportal, 2020; Kemp, 2020; Anil, 2016; and Social Media and the Classroom 2016)	23.81
2. Pedagogical Improvisation and Innovation (Kaptan & Timurlenk, 2012; Social Media and the Classroom, 2012; and Mayer, 2003)	14.29
3. Statistics of Penetration to Social Media (Data Reportal, 2020; Kemp, 2020; and Maslanka, 2017)	14.29
4. Trends of Using Technology in Education (Cuevas, 2017; Aysan, 2015; UK Essays, 2015; Hsin & Cigas, 2013; and Ramey, 2013)	23.81
5. Nature and Characteristics of the Today's Learners (Perez, 2020; Domingo, 2018; and Cuevas, 2017)	14.29
6. Impacts of COVID-19 Pandemic to Education (Li & Lalani, 2020; & Malipot, 2020)	9.52
Total	100

Many studies led out for a fresh and learner-friendly approach in education, as the table above presents. The data were computed using percentage. Twenty-one foreign and local literature were established to explain why the researcher chose vlogs as an innovation to develop.

The literature reviews show positive feedback on the benefits of using vlogs in education (23.81%), such as they had improved the academic performance of learners with great interest and enthusiasm in an enjoyable, comfortable, and relaxed atmosphere. It was supported that using technology (23.81 %) provides new opportunities in teaching and learning a topic effectively. Especially now, a wide range of learners can be reached and helped by vlogs since they have many penetrations to social media (14.29 %). Also, vlogs are one step away from teachers' improvisation and innovation (14.29 %) to attract, prepare, maintain, and retain high-quality education. Hence, bigger problems such as learners' difficulties and loss of interest in understanding the lesson, and background, needs, characteristics, and background (14.29 %) could be catered to. Moreover, vlogs were applicable during the pandemic or alternative delivery mode (ADM), where teachers are physically distant from learners (9.52 %).

Design and Development of Projectile Motion Vlogs

The vlogs' design followed different principles justified in the literature review, aiming to outline what must be considered and catered to. The DBE's recommendation in addressing the mistakes and misconceptions (2011) become the salient feature of the educational vlogs. The said output also followed the 7 E's DOST Star Lesson Plan Exemplar to make sure the flow of instruction was developmentally appropriate.

Moreover, the 7 E's of Instructional Cycle was crafted by DOST Project Star to ensure the effective learning of vital concepts. These "E's" are elicit, engage, explore, explain, elaborate, evaluate, and explain and can be combined or in any order depending

on the lesson's need and background. Hence, the researcher ensured that self-made vlogs were able to achieve their purposes and objectives.

In developing projectile motion vlogs, determining the material resources to be included became one priority. In this case, the material is taken from the learning competency and learner's material of K to 12 Grade 9 Science. Vlogs are made into several parts, as suggested by Mayer's Multimedia Principle, to process the learning of the topic mentally. These are descriptors of motion, Horizontal Dimension of Uniformly Accelerated Motion, Vertical Dimension of Uniformly Accelerated Motion or Free Fall Concept, Projectile Motion (Motion in Two Dimensions), Relationship Between the Launched Angle and the Height, the Range, and the Time of Flight of a Projectile, and Impulse and Momentum.

Notably, the vlogs required a movie editing application like iMovie. iMovie is a video/movie editing tool consisting of images, transitions, animations, and audios organized to make a whole video. With its unique features, this application was used to present vlog contents by combining images, presentations, sounds, and attractive designs so that learners can enjoy watching while learning the concept. Another tool is Adobe Premiere Pro 2020, which was used to create the intro of the vlogs. iPhone 6 and an ordinary headset with a built-in microphone were used to record video narration. Lastly, the keynote was used to create an interactive slide presentation. These tools helped the researcher to achieve his purpose to develop and design vlogs.

Furthermore, scriptwriting was done to make the creation of learning vlogs more focused. Through writing of scripts, important details are valued. Also, scripts ensure a smooth flow presentation of the lesson.

The study also provided a strong belief that teachers can be creative using resources that are already available. However, since the resources were not that advanced, the audio quality was not good in some vlogs due to reasonable and inevitable noises such as rain and barking of dogs. Also, the researcher could not control the time of each vlog due to the difficulty of the topic. Some vlogs lasted for 10 minutes, and some reached 20 minutes. However, the topics were evenly divided into subtopics so learners who have limited attention span and space can comprehend and mentally process bulky topics, as Mayer advised. Mayer's multimedia principle, in which the study is anchored, was used to develop vlogs so that proper images, words, and animations can work together to log in entirely in learners' minds and link them from their experiences or prior knowledge. Thus, making the learning meaningful and relevant is a must.

Lastly, after the vlogs were produced, the uploading of contents on YouTube will follow (YT link: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC_xozCpA1jEmnYGfoINjpQ).

Evaluation of Vlogs

The projectile motion vlogs are evaluated in four dimensions or qualities- content, instructional, technical, and accuracy and up-to datedness information. As explained by Tan (2019), proper evaluation of learning materials will result to quality learning. Below are the results of the evaluation of projectile motion vlogs:

Table 3.
Results of Content Quality

Factors	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	3.64	Very Satisfactory
2. Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	3.58	Very Satisfactory
3. Content is accurate.	3.53	Very Satisfactory
4. Content is up to date.	3.56	Very Satisfactory
5. Content is logically developed and organized.	3.51	Very Satisfactory
6. Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	3.53	Very Satisfactory
7. Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	3.58	Very Satisfactory
8. Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3.58	Very Satisfactory
9. Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	3.53	Very Satisfactory
10. Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	3.58	Very Satisfactory
General WM	3.56	Very Satisfactory
Total Points	35.62	

Note: Resource must score at least 30 points out of a maximum 40 points to pass this criterion. Please put a check mark on the appropriate box

Passed
 Failed

The data reveals a very satisfactory weighted mean of 3.56 in the criterion. This means that the teacher-evaluators find the projectile motion vlogs qualified in terms of their content quality. Hence, 35.62 total score was garnered which is above the minimum points to pass the criterion.

Prominently, Factor 1, “Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended,” yielded the highest weighted mean of 3.64, while Factor 5, “Content is logically developed and organized,” got the lowest weighted mean of 3.51. Both of these factors are interpreted as very satisfactory.

Meanwhile, Factor 2, “Concepts develop contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives,” Factor 7 “Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking,” Factor 8, “Content is relevant to real-life situations,” and Factor 10, “Content promotes positive values that support formative growth” top the second spot.

Table 4.
Results of Instructional Quality

Factors	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Purpose of the material is well defined.	3.51	Very Satisfactory
2. Material achieved its defined purpose.	3.60	Very Satisfactory
3. Content is accurate/ Learning Objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	3.53	Very Satisfactory
4. Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	3.51	Very Satisfactory
5. Graphics/colors/sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	3.42	Satisfactory
6. Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	3.53	Very Satisfactory
7. Material effectively stimulates creativity of target user.	3.51	Very Satisfactory
8. Feedback on target user’s responses is effectively employed.	3.51	Very Satisfactory
9. Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	3.51	Very Satisfactory
10. Instruction is integrated with target user’s previous experience.	3.53	Very Satisfactory
General WM Total Points	3.52 35.18	Very Satisfactory

Note: Resource must score at least 30 points out of a maximum 40 points to pass this criterion. Please put a check mark on the appropriate box

Passed
 Failed

The data reveals a very satisfactory weighted mean of 3.52 in the criterion. This means that teacher-evaluators find the projectile motion vlogs qualified in terms of their

instructional quality. Hence, 35.18 total score was garnered which is above the minimum points to pass the criterion.

Teacher-made vlogs achieved its defined purpose (Factor 2) yielded a weighted mean of 3.60. However, Factor 5, “Graphics/colors/sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons,” must be given more attention since it is the lowest among other factors with a mean of 3.42. Though, both factors are interpreted as very satisfactory.

Meanwhile, Factor 3 (Content is accurate/Learning objectives are clearly stated.), Factor 6 (Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.), and Factor 10 (Instruction is integrated with target user’s previous experience) rank second.

Table 5.
Results of Technical Quality

Factors	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Audio enhances understanding of the concept	3.40	Satisfactory
2. Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) is clear and can be easily understood.	3.47	Satisfactory
3. There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals, if any.	3.38	Satisfactory
4. Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	3.44	Satisfactory
5. Screen displays (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	3.47	Satisfactory
6. Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret.	3.51	Very Satisfactory
7. Visuals sustain interest and do not distract user’s attention.	3.49	Satisfactory
8. Visuals provide accurate representation of the concept discussed.	3.40	Satisfactory
9. The user support materials (if any) are effective.	3.44	Satisfactory
10. The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material.	3.42	Satisfactory
11. The material can easily and independently be used.	3.49	Satisfactory
12. The material will run using minimum system requirements.	3.44	Satisfactory
13. The program is free from technical problems.	3.40	Satisfactory
General WM	3.44	Satisfactory
Total Points	44.76	

Note: Resource must score at least 30 points out of a maximum 40 points to pass this criterion. Please put a check mark on the appropriate box

Passed
 Failed

The data present that the study's learning material passed the technical quality standards with 44.76 total points that is above the given score. Also, a satisfactory rating of 3.44 was garnered where Factor 6, "Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret," yielded the highest mean of 3.60 and interpreted as very satisfactory; and Factor 3, "There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals, if any," got the lowest mean of 3.38.

Meanwhile, Factor 7 (Visual sustain interest and do not distract user's attention), and Factor 11 (The material can easily and independently be used) top the second spot.

Table 6.

Results of Accuracy and Up-to-Date Information Quality

Factors	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Conceptual errors.	3.42	Present but with minor revisions
2. Factual errors.	3.47	Present but with minor revisions
3. Grammatical and/or typographical errors.	3.47	Present but with minor revisions
4. Other errors (i.e., computational errors, obsolete information, errors in the visuals, etc.)	3.60	Not Present
General WM Total Points	3.49 13.96	Present but with minor revisions

Note: Resource must score at least 16 points out of a maximum 16 points to pass this criterion. Please put a check mark on the appropriate box

Passed
 Failed

Accuracy and up-to-datedness information and its determining factors are shown in the table where 3.49 mean was achieved. A failing mark with 13.96 score that is below the perfect score (16) was determined.

The teacher-evaluators were satisfied that Factor 4, "Other errors (i.e., computational errors, obsolete information, errors in the visuals, etc.)," was not traced throughout the vlogs and garnered the highest mean of 3.60. Meanwhile, Factor 1, "Conceptual errors" got the lowest mean of 3.42.

Moreover, Factor 2 (Factual Errors) and Factor 3 (Grammatical and/or typographical errors) garner the same mean of 3.47 and take the second spot.

Comments and Suggestions for Improvement.

The respondents' comments and suggestions are arranged into five (5) themes. These comments and suggestions are aimed to improve better the study and the output of the study itself.

Table 7.

Comments and Suggestions of Respondents for Improvement

Theme	Percentage
1. No comment	53.33
2. Technicality Issues	17.78
3. Context and Concepts Improvement	6.67
4. Positive Review	15.56
5. Impact to Learners	6.67
Total	100

Among the comments and suggestions, the highest percentage is “No Comment,” with a 53.33% rate. Meanwhile, 17.78% of the response encouraged the researcher to improve the materials' technical issues such as audio-video narration and editing. Respondents also gave positive reviews on the researcher's effort to promote Science learning in an appealing manner, which has a percentage of 15.56%. Lastly, both context and concept improvements and impact to learners yielded the same rate of 6.67%

DISCUSSION

Notable Considerations in Selecting Projectile Motion as Topic Content

The test results for three consecutive school years identified that projectile motion is the least learned topic that requires major intervention. It also reveals that learners found the topic difficult because they committed mistakes in answering projectile motion problems and did not have enough Science processes and skills to comprehend such advanced lessons.

Despite pre-requisite topics learned from previous grade levels, learners still find it difficult. This difficulty is due to the common mistakes committed to solving projectile motion problems identified by the Department of Basic Education (Mudau, 2014). These mistakes were identified from the learners' responses from 2008-2010. Among these mistakes were: using inappropriate sign conventions, solving without understanding the vertical and horizontal components, and learning without application of the topic in real-life situations.

The 2019 PISA Results interpreted that Filipino Science learners cannot go on higher Science education because they lacked fundamentals. These fundamentals are skills and expected to help the learners in learning projectile motion. Hence, Mudau (2017) and Tigere (2014) elaborated on the significance of critical thinking, mathematical ability, vocabulary, and many more for this topic. Therefore, learners without these skills may find the topic difficult and commit mistakes eventually. Likewise, the need to acquire or reacquire the said skills is advisable (Bhakti et al., 2019; Nizoloman, 2013; Grosser & Nel, 2013; Cohen, 2012; Setati, 2011).

As a result, educators are encouraged to double their effort to address these dilemmas and to further increase the knowledge of projectile motion among learners. Therefore, these understandings convinced the researcher that projectile motion is the best choice to select as the vlog content.

Analysis of the Need for Vlogs

Vlogs, as defined, are records of thoughts, experiences, and opinions that vloggers or content creators filmed and published on the internet (Frobenius, 2014; Christensson, 2011; & Buenaventura, 2015). These materials can relate and deliver information that is most tangible to learners.

The items or indicators “benefits of vlogs in learning a topic” and “trends in using technology in education” top the statistics. This means incorporating new opportunities in education through technologies like the materials is highly encouraged (Ramey, 2013). Specifically, Anil (2016) and Darmawan (2016) pointed out that vlogs greatly improved the learning of a topic with great interest and enthusiasm in an enjoyable, comfortable, and relaxed learning atmosphere. Moreover, the use of new technologies in education effectively taught the new breed of learners (Aysan, 2015; & Hsin & Cigas, 2013).

Besides these, millions of learners worldwide are into vlogging sites (YouTube, Facebook, TikTok, etc.). Therefore, a wide range of learners who are experiencing difficulty in learning a topic could be reached and helped if teachers would upload educational content (Data Reportal, 2020; Kemp, 2020; & Maslanka, 2017). Thus, the “statistics of penetration to social media,” together with the “nature and characteristics of today’s learners” and the “pedagogical improvisation and innovation,” rank second. This connotes that teachers are urged to reinvent their pedagogical approaches from traditional to modern methods to keep on track with their learners’ needs and interests (Kaptan & Timurlenk, 2012; Perez, 2020; & Cuevas, 2017) especially the learners of today who are very expressive and entitled about themselves (Domingo, 2018).

To attract learners and produce and maintain high-quality teaching, educators also need to vary instruction and incorporate as many senses as possible since the multisensory approach effectively facilitates learning retention (Social Media and the

Classroom, 2012; & Mayer, 2003). Hence, vlogs can also help the teachers be creative, innovative, and updated on their teaching styles and skills, especially in teaching the least learned topics.

Since vlogs were uploaded on social media (YouTube), learners could learn a topic without limitations because they would not mind class performance. Other issues such as the convenience of learners in learning a lesson are catered since they have time to watch and rewatch the topic in which classroom setting discussion cannot offer. However, teachers are encouraged to provide soft copies in flash disks or CDs to modular or offline learners since they have no means for online-distance education.

Lastly, a more difficult situation appeared when the COVID-19 pandemic affects education and the need to reinvent pedagogies that are as effective as the preceding ones become prominent. By uploading on YouTube and saving on flash disks, vlogs are fitted for distance learning since teachers and learners are geographically distant (Li and Lalani, 2020; & Malipot, 2020). Therefore, no doubt that the need to develop a powerful technique to improve the learning of the least learned topics is highly encouraged. The researcher believes that this kind of learning materials in education will be helpful due to its overflowing benefits.

Design and Development of Projectile Motion Vlogs

The design and development of projectile motion vlogs followed the suggestion of DBE on how to minimize the learners' mistakes in solving projectile problems. The vlogs utilized 7 E's DOST Lesson Plan Exemplar format to ensure a developmentally sequenced topic presentation. Akanwa and Ovute (2014) pointed out that this model can impact learners' achievement and interest since the activities are towards investigation. The study also ensured that teachers could be creative in their pedagogy using materials that are already available. The researcher used only a smartphone and laptop to record audio-video narration, make a presentation and edit the whole vlogs. Vlogs were divided into several parts, and the study applied the multimedia principle so that learners could mentally process the learning of the topic, as suggested by Mayer's CTML, in which the study was anchored.

Evaluation of Vlogs

Content Quality

The material passed the content quality with a very satisfactory rating respectively with scores above the passing rate. This means that the projectile motion vlogs are congruent and consistent with the learning competencies as mandated in the curriculum. According to Hamidova and Ganiyeva (2020), learning objectives must be taken into account in selecting a content because the right content will help to achieve goals. This view of Hamidova and Ganiyeva supported the study of Dela Cruz (2015), which stated

that materials must have relevance with the objectives of the lesson. In which the vlogs provide, therefore, it can be used as support system to achieve the competencies of the lesson.

Also, the content is suitable for learners since it can provide holistic growth. Hence, the researcher is encouraged to plan, manage, and implement a more developmentally sequenced vlog to improve the learning competencies. Likewise, school heads and administrators are encouraged to continuously improve and strengthen their teachers' pedagogy to ensure quality teaching (Friesen et al., 2015).

Moreover, content quality is an essential aspect in selecting instructional material (IM) since it gives the idea that the materials used for instruction must be aligned to curriculum standards and has an appropriate depth of knowledge. So, teachers are encouraged to select materials that possess this quality. This notion is congruent to the study of Pourhosein and Sabouri (2016) that a highly motivated and well-trained teacher can select appropriate materials and activities for their learners. Also, IMs should engage and respect the learners' needs, interest, and nature (Bugler et al., 2017).

Instructional Quality

The material passed the instructional quality with a very satisfactory rating respectively with scores above the passing rate. This tells that the respondents have a positive perception to the created vlogs. This also implies that if the teacher would incorporate the material to the student, it could meet the curriculum requirements and attract learners if visuals, graphics, and sounds are good. Teachers, assisted by school leaders, are therefore encouraged to attend ICT seminars and workshops to enhance their teaching using technologies in education and solve the ICT skill gap during the pandemic (Montoya, 2020).

According to Bugler et al. (2017), it is important that the learning materials can engage and motivate the learners so that they can relate the lessons in real-life situations. Since the respondents find the projectile motion vlogs engaging, the notion recommended by Bugler et al. is satisfied.

Likewise, Martin and Bolliger (2018) highlighted that if students are well engaged, students are satisfied and motivated. Also, they noted that students' engagement can reduce the sense of isolation and further improve the students' performance especially now where everything is online. Therefore, a material that is easy to use, learner-friendly, and can support learners' learning progress is a good sign that instructional quality is achieved (Bugler et al., 2017).

Technical Quality

The material passed the instructional quality with a satisfactory rating respectively with scores above the passing rate. This reveals that the projectile motion vlogs can attract learning and provide independent learning. As suggested by Tomita (2017), learning materials should be displayed in various forms so that learners with diverse visual needs are also catered. However, the vlogs can be improved more by providing clear and precise sound narration to accompany the good visual presentations.

Bugler et al. (2017) and El Mhoti (2013) reiterated that a good instructional material has a strong visual appeal with appropriate and suitable graphics and aesthetics that could support and enhance learners' assimilation of knowledge. Hence, Olurinola (2015) specified that colors have a positive impact on the learners' attention and retention. Aspen Institute (2018) also pointed out that high-quality instructional materials significantly impact learners' academic performance. Moreover, Bugler et al. (2017) stated that visual appeal is an important attribute to engage the learner more.

Accuracy and Up-to-Date Information Quality

Respondents advised improving the materials' accuracy and up-to-datedness information since it did not pass the criterion or achieve the perfect score of 16. It means that in some parts of the projectile motion vlogs, errors are seen, and minor revisions are needed to pass the criterion since this was the first attempt of the researcher to produce this kind of concept.

Moreover, presenting the topic more in a contextualized approach is encouraged. This is also the respondents' suggestion to improve the output of the study and pass the criterion. This means that maybe the vocabulary used was not ideal for the learners as perceived by the evaluators. This perception might be due to lengthy explanations. Also, the created vlogs may contain unclear illustration or obsolete information. Therefore, the researcher must double check where these errors are and provide action for so that this criterion would be satisfied.

Also, as advised by the DEPEDLRMDS from which the tool was adopted, materials that do not pass in any criterion may be subject to modification and may follow LRMDS Development and Production Quality Assurance Processes. This concludes that even the material passed the content, instructional, and technical qualities, it is advisable that accuracy and up-to-datedness information are still addressed. Likewise, quality assured materials do not mean perfect material (Pitsoe & Maila, 2014). Since it is an important criterion, the researcher would look into this to provide an error-free learning material before implementing it (Kanori et al., 2020). Hence, Chinwendu (2014) explained that teaching materials with lexicosyntax errors must be fixed so that errors would not result to more errors. Moreover, proper evaluation of learning materials will lead to quality learning (Tan, 2019).

Comments and Suggestions for Improvement

The data reveal that the respondents encouraged the researcher to improve the materials' technical aspects such as audio-video narration and editing. Hence, this suggests that teachers are fully aware that graphics and aesthetics can impact learning (Bugler et al., 2017).

The researcher's effort to promote Science learning in an appealing manner with was seen by the respondents and implies that they have positive outlook that the researcher will be able to achieve his purpose of improving the knowledge of the least learned and incorporating the use of vlogs as new educational video material. This also denotes that respondents believed that projectile motion vlogs could significantly impact the learners if minor concerns were catered to, such as contextualizing the lessons. It means that if errors and inconsistencies are supplied it will not result to more errors (Chinwendu, 2014). Also as confirmed by Kanori et al. (2020), an error-free material guarantees high quality material. In terms of contextualizing the content, Tolbert (2016) concluded that contextualizing lessons especially Science activities provide a more meaningful learners' engagement in Science learning experience.

Furthermore, this concludes that the material is also relevant during the pandemic or in alternative delivery mode (ADM) where teaching and learning process is mostly done through online. Meanwhile, it can be deduced that "No Comment" may be considered as null data. However, it also affirms that more than half of the respondents refused to comment and suggest and let the evaluation results speak for themselves.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The projectile motion is a least learned competency identified from the test results for three consecutive school years and needed to be improved to address common mistakes committed by the learner and develop scientific process skills. Hence, it was selected as the topic content of the study;
2. Education needs versatile and potent tools to address major educational issues of today. There are records of the benefits of using vlogs in education, and this kind of technology plays a vital role in today's educational arena. Moreover, vlogs provide the teachers with a capacity to improve and innovate pedagogies, to target learners' needs, characteristics, and backgrounds, such as their convenience in learning a lesson due to class size and limited school time. Especially, a wide range of learners has direct penetration to social media. Lastly, the drastic change brought by the COVID-19 pandemic, where distance learning is the only applicable strategy, was taken into account;

3. The projectile motion vlogs utilized simple tools such as a smartphone and laptop for audio-video recording and editing. It followed the DBE's suggestion on how teachers can address the common mistakes in solving projectile motion problems. It also incorporated the 7 E's DOST Lesson Plan Exemplar to provide a developmentally sequenced presentation of topics. Moreover, vlogs were split into parts and applied the multimedia principle of Mayer to allow the learners mentally process the acquisition of the topic;
4. The evaluation revealed that the materials are quality assured in terms of content, instructional, and technical qualities with scores that exceeded the passing rate. However, before implementing the vlogs to the learners, minor revisions or modifications must be catered to since respondents have seen several errors in the accuracy and up-to-datedness information in some parts of the vlogs; and
5. Respondents commended the researcher's effort to promote Science education creatively. However, they suggested enhancing audio-video quality, focusing better on filming, and editing, adding engaging pictures and animations, and incorporating knowledge through contextualization and conceptualization to improve the material's features further. Moreover, more than half of the respondents refused to give comments and suggestions and let the study results speak for themselves.

Recommendations

Based on conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Teachers are encouraged to review, focus, and improve projectile motion or other learning competencies in Science and any subject area that are considered least learned. They may employ the outputs of this study or devise a different instructional approach to provide a variety of learning materials and strategies;
2. Teachers, who believe in the potency of the outputs of the study, may utilize it and advise to improve the audio-video quality of the material by using equipment, gadgets, and applications intended for the creation of vlogs;
3. The projectile motion vlogs are suggested for modification since there were errors seen on the accuracy and up-to-datedness information that require minor revisions using the LRMS Development and Production Quality Assurance Processes or any modification approach before undergoing implementation;
4. Teaching strategies need to be diversified to address the learning needs and problems encountered by learners. Also, to enhance the learning of Science concepts and thus improve the learners' academic performance;

5. Learners are also recommended to create their learning vlogs to motivationally support the education of topics that seem to be difficult for them, and also to evaluate how much concepts and skills are retained in their mind since vlog is versatile;

6. School leaders are advised to provide in-service training to teachers so that they can gain new insights and trends in teaching Science, primarily pedagogical approaches that are applicable in the new normal of education where teachers are geographically distant from the learners;

7. Curriculum experts and planners, especially module writers, are prompt to incorporate the use of vlogs and other instructional videos as a tool for empowering learners' learning experience and capacity since these are accepted and evaluated positively by the respondents; and

8. Lastly, the future researchers are highly encouraged to evaluate the outputs with other experts such as curriculum and instructional experts, and test whether the vlogs can effectively improve the knowledge of the topic.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The data collection of the study involved the processes of ethical considerations.

Before the data gathering, the researcher asked his adviser and statistician permission and statistics to make the research better.

The study's adopted instrument was approved by the panel members before the deployment procedure to ensure validity and reliability. Consent letters were also given and approved by the school heads of participating schools so that the participants were ensured that they knew who the researcher is, the organization he is involved with, and the reason for collecting data. These were also appended in the survey form before the question proper.

Also, the participants' permission was accentuated, so they should be aware that their study's involvement is voluntary. The study also made the participants aware that the information they provided as confidential, and their names were kept anonymous. Since the google form was used in the process, the researcher intentionally locked the "see-other-results" function to secure that other participants could not access others' personal information. When possible and applicable, the sharing of the results back to the participants would be served after the data had been analyzed.

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